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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

A SIBYL CALLED CIMMERIAN: EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL
LINK TO THE APENNINE SIBYL¹

1. Cumae and Norcia

The Apennine Sibyl, or the Sibyl of Norcia, has been the focus of fascinated attention throughout many centuries, from the fifteenth-century romance *Guerrino The Wretch* by Andrea da Barberino to the late nineteenth-century explorations carried out by the philologist Pio Rajna, and beyond. Dozens and dozens of literary works have mentioned her name and whereabouts, depicting an oracle who would be concealed under the rocky bulk of Mount Sibyl, in the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Italian Apennines.

Fig. 1 - A vista on Mount Sibyl, the peak in the Italian Apennines

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According to Andrea da Barberino, the Apennine Sibyl is to be identified with the Cumaean Sibyl, a classical Sibyl who is included in the ancient enumeration provided by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius, an author who lived in the fourth century. In the work written by Andrea da Barberino, it's the Sibyl herself who openly declares her own origin:

«I want you to know my name. I was called 'Cumaean' by the Romans for I was born in a town in the countryside whose name is Cumae: before I was sentenced to this place I lived in the world one thousand two hundred years. When Aeneas came to Italy, I led him through the nether world: and I was seven hundred years old at that time [...] And in his time [of Tarquinius Priscus] the Romans came and asked me for laws: and I sent nine books of laws to them. And in that time to my own benefit I asked to remain alive, as much as the world could ever last, until the fair judge will come for the last judgment».

[In the original Italian text: «Io voglio che tu sapi el mio nome. Io fui chiamata da Romani chumana per che io naqui in una città de campagna che ha nome chumana: e stete al mondo inanzi che io fosse iudicata in questa parte mille e ducento anni, che quando Enea vene i queste parte zoe in Italia, io lo menai per tuto lo inferno: e havea alhora sete cento anni [...] E nel suo tempo mandareno li Romani a domandare lezie: et io mandai a loro nove libri de lezie. Et in quello tempo per mia scientia mandai a domandare de stare in questa vita: tanto quanto el mondo de durare, et che el dreto iudice vignerà a giudicare»].

In the above excerpt, the main features which the ancient Roman tradition attributed to the Cumaean Sibyl are all mentioned by Andrea da Barberino: her role as a guide to the Otherworld as portrayed in Publius Vergilius Maro's *Aeneid* (Book 6); the nine books of sibilline prophecies offered to King Tarquinius, as reported by Lactantius; the legendary tale about her immortality, which is narrated by Publius Ovidius Naso in his *Metamorphoses*.

Andrea da Barberino also provides an explanation as to the reason for which the Cumaean Sibyl would have moved her abode to a mountain in central Italy. The Sibyl says that she was «sentenced there», a wording that refers to another old lore, dating to the early Christian era: the Sibyl, a virgin like the Holy Mary and her teacher, had conceived the whim that she

could be the one to grow the son of God in her own womb; but God himself, who had already chosen Mary, devised to punish her for her unholy arrogance. And when Guerrino asks for information about the whereabouts of the Sibyl, a man tells him that

Fig. 2 - The passage on the Cumaean Sibyl which appears in a manuscripted version of Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* published in Venice in 1480

«I heard that the wise Sibyl was a virginal maid, so that she had hoped that God would enter into her when the Incarnation occurred in the Holy Mary. Because of that different choice she grieved and was then sentenced amid these mountainous ridges».

[In the original Italian text: «Io ho udito dir che ze la savia Sibilla la quale si è vergene in lo mondo che la credea che dio scendesse i(n) lei qua(n)do incarnò in Maria vergine. E per questo lei desperò e fu ziudicata per questa casone in queste montagne»].

But Guerrino's Sibyl is eager to stress that she herself has nothing to do with the Holy Mary, because that was a story connected to another Sibyl,

the Albunean (better known as the Tiburtine Sibyl). When Guerrino asks the oracle whether she is the one who «was granted by the grace of God to be the teacher of the virgin who gave birth to the Saviour of our human nature» («havendoti conceduta la divina providentia la gratia che tu fosti maestra de quela verzene in cui incarnò el Salvatore de la humana natura» in Italian), the Sibyl replies harshly to him, by saying that she

«[...] has never been the one who taught our lady [...] The Sibyl you are referring to is called Albunea».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] ella non essere stata quella che insegna a nostra donna [...] La Sibilla che tu voi dire have nome Albunea»].

In the sixteenth century, the Cumaean origin of the Apennine Sibyl is mentioned by Ludovico Ariosto as well. The author of *Orlando Furioso* writes the following words:

«[...] the Cumæan Sibyl [...] who fled, in antiquity, to a Cavern in the territory of Norcia, placed on a mountain-top amidst a gloomy forest, from the charming abode she used to live in at earlier times».

[In the original Italian text: «la Sibilla Cumea, la qual ridotta / s'era in quei tempi a la Nursina grotta / su gli aspri monti in una selva folta / da i luoghi ameni, ove habitava prima»].

The Apennine Sibyl and the Cumaean: a close relationship seems to exist between the two. However, we also have the evidence of a second, different tradition, emerging from a different work written in 1568.

The work is the *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*, written by Francesco Maurolico, and it tells us a different story. According to Maurolico, the Sibyl of Norcia is to be identified with another Sibyl: the Cimmerian.

Who is the Cimmerian Sibyl? Is she included in the classical list of ten Sibyls handed over to us by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius in the fourth century? And what does Maurolico says about a potential link connecting the Cimmerian Sibyl and the Sibyl of Norcia?

We will now try and tread a new mysterious path in the legends and lore of Sibyls. Don't miss the chance to further step ahead in the enthralling, hidden enigma of the Apennine Sibyl.

2. *A Cimmerian connection*

In the fifteenth-century romance *Guerrino The Wretch*, Andrea da Barberino presents a Sibyl who lives under a mountain in the vicinity of Norcia: an oracle who declares that she is the Cumaean Sibyl, after having established her abode in the Apennine ridge, far from the ancient town of Cumae.

However, Francesco Maurolico, an abbot and scholar who lived in Messina (southern Italy) in the sixteenth century, does not agree with such an identification at all. In a number of different passages from his *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*, published in 1568, he clearly states that the Apennine Sibyl is to be considered as the Cimmerian Sibyl, one of the ten classical oracles listed in Lactantius' most renowned *De Divinis Institutionibus*, a work written in the fourth century.

In a previous paper, we already published Maurolico's mentions concerning the Sibyl of Norcia; we review all of them here, for the reader's convenience:

«Ameria, an Italian town set in the Sabine region. From this town the author names the 'Emerian Sibyl', who others call the 'Cimeriam' owing to the uncertainty of the place; she lives in the caverns of Norcia, and is different from both the Cumaean and the Tiburtine Sibyls [...] Norcia, a town of the Italian region of Picenum; close to it is the Cavern of the Cimeriam Sibyl, and the lake of Demons [...] The fourth Sibyl is the Cumaean, whom Naevius mentions in his books about the Punic war, and Piso in his annals as well; from the Cimeriam castle, also known as the Cave of Norcia, which some call by the corrupted name of 'Cynea' or 'Cymica' [...] Cumae, a town of Campania lying by the gulf of Baiae. Here was the Cumaean Sibyl, who was also called Deiphobe, and by some named as Cimmeria or Cymica, but in truth the latter is a different one in the cavern of Norcia».

[In the original Latin excerpts: «Ameria civitas Italiae in Sabinis. Hinc denominat author Sybillam Emeriam, quam alii Cimeriam vocant ab obscuritate loci, et in Nurcinis antris habitantem, atque a Cumana, et a Tyburtina diversam [...] Nurcia civitas Italiae in agro Piceno, iuxta quam est Antrum Sibyllae Cymeriae, et lacus Daemonum [...] Quartam Cumaema in Italia, quam Nevius in libris belli punici, Piso autem in annalibus nominat; ex Cimerio oppido, sive Antro nurcino, quae corrupto forte verbo Cymea, vel Cymica vocetur a nonnullis [...] Cumae Campaniae civitas in sinu Baiarum. Hic fuit Cumana Sibylla, quae Deiphobe vocatur, quae a nonnullis Cimmerica, vel Cymica dicitur, nisi haec alia sit ex antro Nurcino»].

Fig. 3 - Francesco Maurolico's *Martyrologium*, the original edition published in Venice in 1568, with the addendum on the *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum* which contains a number of passages on the Sibyl of Norcia

In Maurolico's *Topographia*, a catalogue of places connected to the presence of God on earth, he repeatedly states that the Sibyl of Norcia has nothing to do with the Cumaean Sibyl, as her lineage goes back to a very different classical Sibyl. He shows no hesitation: the Sibyl of Norcia is the

Emeriam - or Cimeriam, Cymeriam, Cymea, Cymica, Cimmeria - who lived in ancient times in a small town called Ameria or Cimeria, lying not far from Norcia, where the Sibyl's cave stands.

Was Francesco Maurolico right? Was a village named Ameria or Cimeria really extant in the vicinity of Norcia? Is the Sibyl of the Apennines really descending from a Cimmerian Sibyl? And what does 'Cimmerian Sibyl' stand for?

In a preceding article, we saw that Maurolico did not take the above information from his recognised primary source, Jean Germain's *Mappemonde Spirituelle*, a work written in the fifteenth century. Furthermore, in addition to what we stated in that article, we can now show that Maurolico drew part of the information he wrote on the fourth Sibyl from another fifteenth-century work (whom Maurolico himself mentions in his introductory notes to his *Topographia*). As a matter of fact, we find almost the same wording used by Maurolico as to the «Ameria civitas» in Claudius Ptolemaeus' *Cosmographia*, in the version published in 1484 in Ulm by Johann Reger. This book contains an introductory «Registrum Alphabeticum» listing a large number of geographical names referred to by Ptolemy, and - under letter 'A' - we find the following:

«Ameria (Book 3, Chapter 1, Map 6 of Europe). Here the fourth Sibyl was born. The Emerian Sibyl was born in Italy and is also known as Chemical, wearing a heavenly golden garment, with long parted hair down to her shoulders, and young; of her Ennius reports: in the first period of the Virgin, a young lady of charming aspect and long hair will rise, sitting on a throne and feeding a child with a right nourishment, a milk sent down from heaven».

[In the original Latin text: «Ameria li 3 ca 1 ta 6 europe Hic nascitur quarta sibilla. Sibilla emeriana in ytaliam nata, alias chimica vestita celestia veste, de aurata capillis per scapulas spartis et iuvenis, de qua enni ait. In prima facie virginis ascendit puella pulchra facie, plixa capillis, sedens super sedem stratam nutrit puerum, dans ei ad comedendum ius proprium, id est lac de celo missum»].

What does it all mean? Who is the fourth Sibyl? Why is she portrayed in a such a peculiar way? And why Maurolico seems to quote from this excerpt

when he mentions the unknown town of «Ameria», although no reference is found in Reger's Ptolemy as to Norcia and its Sibyl's cave?

Fig. 4 - The excerpt on 'Ameria' and the fourth Sibyl as it appears in Johann Reger's *Cosmographia* from Ptolemy, a book published in Ulm in 1486

The matter is very complex and, at first sight, utterly puzzling. However, we will try to solve the many riddles concealed in the above excerpts, conferring an identity and a place of birth to the fourth Sibyl, the Cimmerian.

For a better understanding of the issue, we need to go back to Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' enumeration of ten classical Sibyls, and meet, in a close encounter, the original Cimmerian Sibyl.

3. The enigmatic fourth Sibyl

Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius, a fourth-century early-Christian author, was by no means a minor personage: he was a high-rank advisor to Emperor Constantine the Great and tutor to Emperor's son Crispus.

In his most famous work, *De Divinis Institutionibus*, he provides a remarkable quote drawn from Marcus Terentius Varro, who in turn, in a book that has now gone lost, set down what is considered as the canonical list of ten Sibyls belonging to ancient, classical times.

«It is known that Sibyls were ten in number. Marcus Varro enumerated them all under the writers, who wrote an account of each. The first was from the Persians, and of her Nicanor made mention, who wrote the deeds of Alexander of Macedon. The second was of Libya...»

Fig. 5 - The excerpt on the Sibyls as it appears in a most valuable edition of Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius *De Divinis Institutionibus*, printed in 1465 at the benedictine abbey of Subiaco (Italy)

[In the original Latin text: «Ceterum Sibillas decem numero fuisse. Easquem omnes [M. Varro] numeravit sub auctoribus, qui de singulis scriptitarunt. Primam fuisse de Persis, cujus mentionem fecerit Nicanor, qui res gestas Alexandri Macedonis scripsit. Secundam Libicam...»].

Such are the words by Lactantius, which we will review in further detail in a future article. For the time being, it is sufficient to analyse what he declares about the Cumaean Sibyl and her Cimmerian counterpart.

The following are Lactantius's words on the Sibyl from Cumae, as taken from a most valuable edition of *De Divinis Institutionibus* printed in 1465 at the benedictine abbey of Subiaco (Italy) and reporting the renowned episode of the books offered to the King of Rome by the clever oracle:

«... The seventh was of Cumae, by name Amalthea, who is termed by some Demophile and they say that she brought nine books to the king Tarquinius Priscus, and asked for them three hundred philippics [a golden currency from the antique kingdom of Macedon], and that the king refused so great a price, and derided the madness of the woman; that she, in the sight of the king, burnt three of the books, and demanded the same price for those which were left; that Tarquinius much more considered the woman to be mad; and that when she again, having burnt three other books, persisted in asking the same price, the king was moved, and bought the remaining books for the three hundred pieces of gold: and the number of these books was afterwards increased, after the rebuilding of the Capitol; because they were collected from all cities of Italy and Greece, and especially from those of Erythrae, and were brought to Rome, under the name of whatever Sibyl they were».

[In the original Latin text: «Septimam Cumanam nomine Amaltheam, quae ab aliis Demophile nominatur; eamque novem libros attulisse ad regem Tarquinium priscum, ac pro eis trecentos philippeos postulasse; regemque aspernatum pretii magnitudinem, derisisse mulieris insaniam: illam in conspectu regis tres combussisse, ac pro reliquis idem pretium postulasse: Tarquinium multo magis mulierem insanire putasse. Quae denuo tribus aliis exustis, cum in eodem pretio perseveraret, motum esse regem, ac residuos trecentis aureis emisse: quorum postea numerus sit auctus, Capitolio refecto, quod ex omnibus civitatibus et Italicis, et Graecis, et praecipue

Erythraeis coacti, allatique sunt Romam, cuiuscumque Sibyllae nomine fuerunt»].

That was for the Cumaean; but what about the Cimmerian Sibyl? In the classical enumeration by Lactantius, she stands out at number four, as we can read in a most precious fourteenth-century manuscript of *De Divinis Institutionibus* preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Latin 1665):

«The fourth a Cimmerian in Italy, whom Naevius mentions in his book on the Punic war, and Piso in his annals».

[In the original Latin text: «Quartam Cimmeriam in ytalia, quam Nevius in libris belli punici Piso in annalibus nominat»].

According to Lactantius, the Cimmerian Sibyl - like the Cumaean and the Tiburtine - is an Italian Sibyl. But where was her shrine situated? Perhaps, was it in the Apennines? Lactantius says nothing about that.

Fig. 6 - The fourth Sibyl in a fourteenth-century manuscript of *De Divinis Institutionibus* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France - Latin 1665)

We may possibly turn to the two authors mentioned in this excerpt, «Naevius» and «Piso», from whom Lactantius took the mentions on the

Cimmerian Sibyl. However, their works are unfortunately lost to us, they are not extant anymore, so we cannot read into the pages of their books.

Gnaeus Naevius, an epic poet who was born in Campania in the early third century B.C., was the author of a *Bellum Poenicum*, a poetic work on the First Punic War and the story of the foundation of Rome: only fifty small literary fragments pertaining to this book are available today, and no known fragment mentions the sibilline topic at all.

Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi was a Roman consul in year 133 B.C. As a Latin author, he wrote the *Annales (Chronicles)*, a work on the origin and history of Rome. Piso's books are lost too, and the few extant excerpts are not relevant to Sibyls.

So where should we turn to unveil the origin and whereabouts of the Cimmerian Sibyl?

Fig. 7 - *Cumaeen Sibyl* as portrayed by Domenico Zampieri, known as Domenichino, in 1610 (Rome, Galleria Borghese)

The answer is not too far from us. Or, to be more specific, it is not too far from a place we already know.

That place is not the Apennines, as we would be glad to find out. That place, strange as it may be, is Cumae again: the Cimmerian Sibyl appears to be linked to the Cumaean oracle. Let's go and investigate why.

4. The Sibyl with many names

Is the fourth Sibyl, described by fourth-century author Lactantius in his celebrated enumeration as «Cimmerian», linked in some way to the seventh in the list, the most famous «Cumaean»?

We begin to doubt when we consider different ancient editions of Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus*. Because the fourth Sibyl is not always called 'Cimmeriam', as we found in manuscript Latin 1665 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France.

As a remarkable instance, let's take again the precious edition printed in Subiaco in 1465, one of the first books ever printed in Italy. The excerpt on the fourth Sibyl reads as follows:

Fig. 8 - Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus* (Subiaco, 1465) with the passage on the fourth Sibyl

«Quartam Cumeam in italia, quam neuius in libris belli punici, piso in annalibus nominant».

The fourth Sibyl has turned into a «Cumeam», a qualifier which appears to have some manifest similarity with the Cumaeam Sibyl.

And we find the same qualifier in a manuscripted versions of Lactantius' work as well. If we consider a fine Neapolitan edition, dating to the fifteenth century and written in an elegant Italian script (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 1674), we find the following:

«Quartam Cumeam in italia, quam Nevius in Libris belli punici, Piso in annalibus nominet».

Fig. 9 - Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus*, the passage on the fourth Sibyl as it appears in a manuscripted version written in Naples in the fifteenth century (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Latin 1674)

Again, our Cimmerian Sibyl has become a Cumaeam Sibyl. Note that no reference to any 'Apennine Sibyl' matter can be found at this stage of our search.

And the confusion is not over, because our Sibyl continues to change her attributes. Let's jump in time and space to the renowned benedictine abbey of St. Gall, set at the foot of the Appenzell Alps, in Switzerland. There, in the amazingly gorgeous Library Hall, a jewel of the eighteenth century, is preserved the world's last existing instance of the *Oracula Sibyllina*, a book printed between 1461 and 1465.

The *Oracula Sibyllina* is an early instance of a Christian-oriented rearrangement of the classical list of ten Sibyls set by Lactantius, in the footsteps of such early-Christian authors as Augustine of Hippo and Isidore of Seville, who maintained that Sibyls were included in the vast plan devised by God to announce the Incarnation of Jesus on earth. In this book, for the first time, Sibyls are listed in the number of twelve, with the inclusion of two additional oracles, the Agrippine Sibyl and the European Sibyl.

Here is what St. Gall's book states about our enigmatic Cimmerian Sibyl:

«The Cyemerian Sibyl, eighteen years old, born in Italy, about whom Albumazar the astrologer writes, in a specific prophecy, that a virgin will feed a child».

[In the original Latin text: «Sibilla Cyemeria annorum XVIII in ytaliam nata de qua scribit albumazar astrologus vaticinatur commodo virgo lactat puer»].

Now our Cimmerian Sibyl - just like all other Sibyls - has been fully enrolled as a herald of the coming of Jesus, having also been provided - and the same applies to all other sibylline oracles - with an appropriate prophecy on the subject, contained in the caption positioned below the drawing and describing a maiden (the Holy Mary) that will feed a child (Jesus) with her milk:

«In the first decan of the sign of Virgin, a maiden will rise, honest and pure and handsome in her face, with long hair, sitting in a throne and feeding a child giving milk to him [...] and the child is called among the nations Jesus...».

[In the original Latin text: «In prima facie virginis ascendit virgo quedam honesta et munda et est pulchra facie prolixi capilli sedens super sedem stratam nutriens puerum dans ei ad comedendum lac quem quedam gens vocat Jhesum»].

Fig. 10 - The fourth Sibyl in the *Oracula Sibyllina* (1461 - 1465, St. Gall. Switzerland)

As you can see, the matter is getting increasingly intricate. And who on earth is «Albumazar the astrologer»? This new element concerning the Cimmerian Sibyl will need further investigation, and sure enough it is not the one and only.

Because we find out the our Cimmerian Sibyl enjoys additional names and further alleged quotes as well. Let's enter into the pages of a very rare book: the *Opuscula*, a miscellaneous book written by Filippo Barbieri, a dominican friar born in Siracusa (Sicily) in 1426. In a 1520 printed edition of Barbieri's work, the first three oracles bear the same names as in *De*

Divinis Institutionibus (Persian, Lybian, Delphic); but then, we find other stunning names for the fourth Sibyl:

«Chimerian Sibyl, who was born in Italy and is also known as Chemical, wearing a heavenly golden garment, with long parted hair down to her shoulders, and young; of her Ennius reports the following: in the first period of the Virgin, a young lady of charming aspect and long hair will rise, sitting on a throne and feeding a child with a right nourishment, a milk sent down from heaven».

[In the original Latin text: «Sybilla chimeria in Italia nata, alias Chimica, vestita celestina veste deaurata capillis per scapulas spartis, et iuvenis de qua Ennius sic ait: in prima facie virginis ascendit puella pulchra facie proluxa capillis; sedens super sedem stratam, nutrit puerum, dans ei ad comedendum ius proprium, idest lac de celo missum»].

Fig. 11 - Filippo Barbieri's *Opuscula* (edition 1520), the Cimmerian Sibyl

The Cimmerian, now turned into «Chimerian» and providing almost the same Christian-oriented prophecy we already saw in St. Gall's *Oracula Sibyllina*, has just earned another qualifier: «Chimica» («Chemical» in English), and with this new name she will often appear in subsequent enumerations of Sibyls. We also find that ancient Roman author Ennius is mentioned as a source about this Sibyl, while no «Albumazar astrologer» is referenced here. And we also find here the very same words we had already retrieved in Claudius Ptolemaeus' *Cosmographia*, in the version published in Ulm in 1484 by Johann Reger: «... vestita celestia veste, de aurata capillis per scapulas spartis et iuvenis, de qua enni ait...», one of the sources used by Francesco Maurolico in his passages on the fourth Sibyl.

Thus, our erratic Cimmerian Sibyl seems to shun our investigation: she pops up from time to time across the centuries with different names, attributes and references to literary sources. And we continue to miss any link to the legend and lore of the Apennine Sibyl, a link that only Francesco Maurolico, the Sicilian abbot, seems to allege.

So what can we do now?

There is still a step to take: we need to go back to the very root of the Cimmerian / Cumaean sibilline tale, a track already pointed to our attention by Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus*. We need to return to Cumae, the antique Greek colony established in southern Italy, and the ancestral home of the seventh Sibyl.

And, perhaps, we will find there the answers we are so eagerly looking for.

5. Albumazar and the transformation into a Christian Sibyl

Starting from a series of quotes extracted from Francesco Maurolico's *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*, we are trying to understand whether a Sibyl called 'Cimmerian' might have anything to do with the Sibyl of Norcia, established beneath a mountain in the Italian Apennines, as alleged by Maurolico himself.

Fig. 12 - A commanding view of Mount Sibyl, the peak raising in central Italy which is at the center of an ancient, enigmatic lore

However, in the course of our search we have stumbled upon a number of unexpected obstacles.

To begin with, the Cimmerian Sibyl, included in the classical list of ten Sibyls set down by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius in his *De Divinis Institutionibus*, written in the fourth century, often appears in different editions of this Latin work with the name of «Cumean», an attribute that seems to imply a close relationship with the Sibyl of Cumae, also listed by Lactantius.

An additional problem is that we cannot proceed into an investigation of the classical authors quoted by Lactantius himself as a reference for the Cimmerian Sibyl (i.e. Marcus Varro, Gnaeus Naevius and Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi), because the literary works written by the three of them have not survived, save selected excerpts, thoroughly irrelevant to our search.

If we transfer our investigation to more recent centuries, by perusing ancient, utmostly rare books such as the *Oracula Sibyllina*, preserved at the Abbey of St. Gall in Switzerland, and Filippo Barbieri's *Opuscula*, both printed in the fifteenth century and both mentioning our highly enigmatic Cimmerian Sibyl, we find out that she shows up with different, additional names - «Cyemerian», «Chimerian», «Chimica». Furthermore, she begins

to appear as a Christian oracle who would have announced the coming of Jesus on earth, by providing a sort of vision concerning a young maiden with long hair, sitting on a throne and feeding a child with her milk: a manifest portrait of Jesus and the Holy Mary. And additional authors are also mentioned: Ennius, a writer from ancient Rome, and a certain «Albumazar the astrologer».

At this point of our search, confusion seems to preside over the whole matter in an undisputed way.

Will we ever be able to unwind this tangled matter? Our motto is: despair not. Let's try to unfold the many leaves which veil the traditional lore about the Cimmerian Sibyl, by taking them out one by one.

As a first step, let's start with getting rid of «Albumazar», the astrologer. We will show that he adds nothing to our investigation on the origin of the Cimmerian Sibyl and her potential connection to the Apennines.

Who is 'Albumazar'? Albumazar is Abu Ma'shar, one of the greatest Muslim astronomers of past ages, who lived in Baghdad in the eighth century. He wrote a number of renowned astrological works, including an *Introductorium Maius in Astronomiam*, which was widely known in Europe starting from the twelfth century.

In 1133, Johannes Hispalensis translated the work by Albumazar into Latin. And in manuscript Lat 14704, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France and containing Johannes Hispalensis' translation work, we stumble upon the very origin of the Christian-oriented words that were later attributed to the Cimmerian Sibyl:

«Virgin [the sign of the zodiac] [...] In its first decan [a partition of the sign itself] [...] a maiden will rise, a handsome and honest and pure virgin, with long hair and handsome face, bearing two spikes in her hand; and she sits in a throne and feeds a child giving nourishment to him [...] and the child is called among the nations Jesus...».

[In the original Latin text: «Virgo [...] ascendit in prima facie illius puella [...] et est virgo pulcra atque honesta et munda, prolixi capilli et pulcra facie, habens in manu sua duas spicas; et ipsa sedet super sedem stratam et

nutrit puerum, dans ei ad commendendum ius [...], et vocant ipsum puerum quedam gens Ihesum...»].

Fig. 13 - The passage about the prophecy related to the zodiacal sign of Virgo in the *Introductorium Maius in Astronomiam*, Johannes Hispalensis' Latin translation of the astrological essay by Albumazar (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Lat 14704)

In the excerpt from Albumazar, an astrological sign conveys a vision of things to come, namely the birth of Jesus, a child attended by a pure virgin, the Holy Mary. In the text by Albumazar, no reference to any Sibyl is present at all.

But the chance was too appealing for later Christian scholars: the oracular tale provided by the heathen Albumazar was unbelievably perfect to illustrate the great plan of God concerning the Incarnation. The tender, emotional prophecy on the Holy Mary feeding Jesus, originally presented in connection to the zodiacal sign of Virgin, was perfectly adaptable to a different witness to God's divine scheme: a virginal Sibyl, announcing the new Christian era, as already alleged by Augustine of Hippo centuries earlier.

So Albumazar's tale was adapted to fit one of the Sibyls included in the list by Lactantius, namely the Cimmerian. To the purpose, in St. Gall's *Oracula Sibyllina*, which we saw in the previous paragraph, the Cimmerian Sibyl is portrayed with a sign in which the very same words used by Albumazar are found («In prima facie virginis ascendit virgo quedam honesta et munda et est pulchra facie prolixi capilli...»). And the same we find in Filippo Barbieri's *Opuscula* («... sedens super sedem stratam, nutrit puerum, dans ei ad comedendum ius proprium, idest lac de celo missum»).

And in another translation of Albumazar's *Introductorium in Astronomiam*, published in Venice in 1506, the excerpt on the zodiacal sign of Virgo is accompanied by an image of a virgin, with long hair and spikes in her hand, which is almost indistinguishable by a typical pictorial illustration of a Sibyl.

Fig. 14 - The same passage as it appears in a printed edition of Albumazar's *Introductorium in Astronomiam* (Venice, 1506)

Here we are: the transformation of the Cimmerian / Cumean Sibyl extracted from Lactantius is now completed. By virtue of an evocative text written by an ancient Muslim astrologer, widely known in Europe owing to existing translations of his works into Latin, we now have a Sibyl that acts as a herald on behalf of God, providing an incontrovertible announcement of the future coming of the Salvation.

That's why Albumazar's oracular tale became, in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, a most favourite topic for Christian preachers willing to convince

audiences that the birth of Jesus had been foretold in advance by pagan seers, as noted by some scholars (Marie-Thérèse d'Alverny, 1984). And in subsequent centuries the Cimmerian Sibyl will continue her journey through history properly supplemented with her prophecy, which was usually inscribed in a scroll, as in a fine sixteenth-century frescoed medallion painted on a wall of the 'Room of the Sibyls' at the Casa Cavassa City Museum in Saluzzo (a small town near Turin, Italy).

Fig. 15 - Cimmerian Sibyl, sixteenth-century frescoed medallion, Casa Cavassa City Museum, Saluzzo (Italy)

As a result, the Cimmerian Sibyl has now fully joined the Christian army. However, Albumazar, the Holy Virgin, the child and all the Christian apparatus we have seen above have not helped us in getting one single step closer to the true origin of the Cimmerian Sibyl. That was only a misleading path.

To reach the core of the legend about the Cimmerian Sibyl, we must leave the Christian centuries behind and go back again to classical time.

There, at last, we will find the answers we have been long looking for.

6. *The Cimmerians and their oracle*

We are still on the footsteps of the Cimmerian Sibyl, the fourth oracle mentioned in the classical enumeration provided by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius in the fourth century. A Sibyl that in some versions of Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus* is presented as 'Cumean', a word that brings to the mind of the reader the word 'Cumae', the Campanian town of the Cumaean Sibyl, who in turn is listed under number seven in the list of Lactantius.

So the main question now is: where is the Cimmerian Sibyl from? According to Francesco Maurolico, a sixteenth-century Sicilian author, she would reside by a town called «Ameria» or a village named «Cimerio» lying by the caves of Norcia, so the Cimmerian Sibyl and the Apennine Sibyl would actually be the very same oracle.

But only Maurolico (and a Father Fortunato Ciucci from Norcia, who quotes from Maurolico in the seventeenth century) supports this assumption.

No other similar identification is retrieved in other authors or works, either in the main sources used by Maurolico (the *Mappemonde Spirituelle* by Jean Germain, which we saw in a previous paper) or the *Oracula Sibyllina* and Filippo Barbieri's *Opuscula*.

So, if we want to find the truth, we have no choice left: we have to turn back and return to classical authors.

The key to all that is the nature and identity of the population known as 'Cimmerians'. Today, many people think that Cimmerians were an ancient tribal population who lived in the Caucasus. In fact they are mentioned by

the Greek historian Herodotus, and have become part of a wider, contemporary popular culture thanks to the fictional tales of 'Conan the Cimmerian', written by American author Robert E. Howard, in which Cimmerians are depicted as an offspring of a Celtic, northern-European culture.

But this is only a minor tradition, though the most widely known, concerning the Cimmerians.

Because if we look for Cimmerians in classical literature, we find no Celts and no Caucasus at all: instead, we are transported back to a place we already know. We know it well, owing to a most famous Sibyl.

And this place is Cumae.

Because, if the works by ancient writers such as Gnaeus Naevius and Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi - who mentioned the Cimmerian Sibyl as indicated by Lactantius - are unfortunately lost to us, nonetheless there are still other ancient authors whose works still survive. And they all tell unanimously the same story: Cimmerians lived in southern Italy, namely near Cumae.

Fig. 16 - Ancient Cumae in a map detail taken from the *Tabula Peutingeriana*, a thirteenth-century copy on parchment of an original Roman road map (Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, Codex Vindobonensis 324)

Let's listen to the ancient voices which narrate this amazing tale. And we are about to start with the war cry sent out long ago by Hannibal, the great Carthaginian general:

«Soldiers [...] I implore you to make yourselves once more worthy of the reputation you trail after you; and remember the battle of Cannae!»

[In the original Latin text: «Miles [...] obtestor, dignos iam vosmet reddite vestra quam trahitis fama et revocate in pectore Cannas»].

Such are the words reported to us by Silius Italicus, a Roman consul and poet, who wrote his *Punica* at the end of the first century. In his work, Silius describes the anguish and sense of powerlessness that seized Hannibal's heart after the victorious battle of Cannae, followed by a long, idle stay of his army in the Campanian town of Capua. Hannibal fails in capitalizing on his winning moves against the Romans, while his soldiers lose their strength amid banquets and pleasures.

In this occurrence, Hannibal is led by local aristocrats into a visit of the surrounding region, which contains many wonders and notable places, most of them connected to the volcanic nature of the area. The Carthaginian general is shown Baiae, a fashionable resort lying by the Tyrrhenian sea, and the Lake Lucrinus, also known under the name of 'Cocytus' (just like the river flowing in the Otherworld of ancient Greece), and then Lake Avernus, or 'Styx' (another Greek river of the underworld), and the nearby swamps, loaded with dark legends connected to the realm of deads.

Finally, Hannibal listens to the following words (*Punica*, Chapter XII, v. 130-133, as they appear in an antique 1483 edition printed in Venice):

«Close at hand, wrapped in gloom and sunk for long ages in subterranean mists, the city of the Cimmerians lay deep in earth under a pall of shade; and tales are told about the unfathomed night of that Tartarean city».

[In the original Latin text: «Ac iuxta caligante situ longumque per aevum infernis pressas nebulis pallente sub umbra Cymmerias iacuisse domos noctemque profundam Tartareae narrant urbis»].

Fig. 17 - The Cimmerians as mentioned in *Punica* by Silius Italicus from an antique 1483 edition printed in Venice

The subterranean houses of the Cimmerians. A place of mystery and darkness, which lay in the vicinity of Lake Lucrinus, Lake Avernus, and Baiae.

That is, near Cumae.

The Cimmerians are no Celts. In antiquity, it was in the region of Cumae that was located the Cimmerian town, a place of gloominess and absence of light. Here is how Sextus Pompeius Festus - a second-century writer who wrote a *De Verborum Significatione* (*On the meaning of words*), subsequently integrated by the benedictine monk Paul the Deacon - portrays the mysterious Cimmerians:

«The Cimmerians are a population inhabiting lands which are subject to the cold of death, and lie between Baiae and Cumae, in the region where a low, large valley is encircled by a huge ridge; the place is never reached by the sun, neither in the morning nor in the evening».

[In the original Latin text: «Cimeri dicuntur homines, qui frigoribus occupatas terras incolunt, quales fuerunt inter Baias et Cumas in ea regione,

in qua convallis satis eminenti iugo circumdata est, quae neque matutino, neque vespertino tempore sole contingitur»].

Fig. 18 - The entry on the Cimmerians in Sextus Pompeius Festus' *De Verborum Significatione* from a fifteenth-century manuscript (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Latin 7662)

There is no surviving doubt: Herodotus' Cimmerians might have actually lived in the Caucasus, but they are different 'Cimmerians'. There existed, in ancient Italy, an Italic population that was based in the Campania province, in a region where the land itself was enshrouded in magic, which originated from the volcanic nature of the soil. And many authors report about them.

Pliny the Elder, in his first-century *Naturalis Historia*, says in Book III that «on the coast [we find] Cumae, a Chalcidian colony, Misenum, the port of Baiae, Bacoli, Lake Lucrinus and Lake Avernus, which is near to where once stood the Cimmerian town. We then come to Puteoli, formerly called the colony of Dicaearchia, then the Phlegraean Plains, and the Marsh of Acherusia in the vicinity of Cumae [...] and then Erculaneum, Pompeii...».

[In the original Latin text: «in ora [...] cumae chalcidesium, misenum, portus baianus, bauli, lacus lucrinus et avernus cimmericum iuxta quem oppidum quondam; deinde puteoli colonia dicerachea dicti, postquam phlegei campi. Acherusia palus Cumis vicina [...] herculaneum, pompeii...»].

Fig. 19 - Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis Historia* (Venice, 1469) with the excerpt on Cimmerians

And in the third century, Lycophrone of Chalcis, in his poem *Alexandra* (v. 695), will write of Odysseus, who «pushes himself beyond the burial place of his helmsman Baius [modern Baiiae] and the abode of Cimmerians and the Acherusian plain...», again locating the Cimmerians in the surroundings of Cumae.

δύσμορφον εἰς κηκασμὸν ᾤκισεν τῶσων,
 οἷ μῶλον ὠρόθυναν ἐχθόνοισ Κρόνου.
 Βαίου δ' ἀμείφας τοῦ κυβερνήτου τάφον,
 καὶ Κιμμέρων ἔπαυλα κάχερουσίαν
 ῥόχθοισι κυμαίνουσαν οἴδματος χύσιν,
 Ὅσσαν τε καὶ λέοντος ἀτραπούς βοῶν
 χωστάς, Ὀβριμοῦς τ' ἄλσος οὐδαίας Κόρης,
 Πυρρολεγέας τε ἄειθρον. ἔνθα δῖος ἄναξ

Fig. 20 - Lycophrone of Chalcis, the passage from the poem *Alexandra* in which the Cimmerians are mentioned

But it is Strabo, the Greek geographer and historian, who provides a most comprehensive reference about the Cimmerians in his most renowned *Geographica*, a work written in the first century. In Book V, he describes

Cumae, Cape Miseno, the swamps called 'Acherontia' (another name for a river flowing in the Otherworld of ancient Greece), Baiiae, the Lake Lucrinus, and the shadowy, blood-curdling Lake Avernus:

«Avernus, entirely encircled by ridges above, looming on it from every side but a single point; it is now cultivated, however in old times it was enshrouded by an inaccessible wood made of huge trees, which covered with gloomy, superstitious shade the whole lake».

[In a 1571 Latin translation of the original text in Greek: «Avernus superciliis recta sursum enatis et undique praterquam in aditu imminentibus, ac nunc quidem cultura elaboratis; olim enim sylvia inaccessa magnarum arborum obsita, ob superstitionem ipsum sinum obumbrabant»].

Fig. 21 - *Strabonis Rerum Geographicarum* published in 1571 in Basel, with the passage on Lake Avernus and the Cimmerians

There, according to Strabo, was the abode of Cimmerians, and their oracle:

«People considered Avernum as a place sacred to Pluto, and that Cimmerians lived there [...] Ephorus maintained that this site was of the Cimmerians, about whom he says that they dwell in underground premises, which they call 'clay-made'; and they come to and fro through subterranean tunnels, and by the same way they allow visitors to the oracle which is deeply dug into the ground; they live on the metal ore they mine, and on those who consult the oracle. [...] And in addition to that, there is an ancient custom that those who live by the oracle must never see the sun, as they can only go outside through the crevices in the ground when the night comes».

[In the Latin translation: «Nam et Avernum p loco Plutoni dicato deputabat, et Cimmerios ibi fuisse indicatu habitare [...] Ephorus vero Cimmeriis locum illum dicans, hos abitare ait in subterraneis aedificiis, quas argillas vocent, ac per fossas quasdam inter se comeare, hospitesque eadem via in oraculum adducere alte infra terram conditum, victum eos metallis effodiendis quarere, et ab ii accipere qui oraculum consulunt [...]. Porro qui apud oraculum illud degunt, eos more a maioribus accepto nunquam videre solem sed noctu ex hiatibus terrae prodire»].

We are getting closer and closer to the true origin of the Cimmerian Sibyl. We have come to Cumae and by the shore of Lake Avernus, in the Italian region of Campania. And we know that the mysterious, almost mythical Cimmerians lived in underground dwellings, and controlled an oracle, deeply set in a subterranean shrine.

Was that oracle a Sibyl?

Yes it was. It was a Cimmerian Sibyl. As we will discover in the next paragraph.

7. A subterranean Sibyl at the Lake Avernus

By following the footprints left by the Cimmerian Sibyl throughout the centuries, we have come back to the classical age, when southern Italy was

the magical scenario for colonies established by settlers moving from Greece.

In the seaside region set between Cumae, Mount Procida with Cape Misenus, Baiiae and Pozzuoli, lay an area which was the realm of mighty subterranean powers: a volcanic area, fully active at that time as it is today, and where the gloomy Lake Avernus stood, surrounded by looming hills and protected by an impenetrable forest. There, an antique population had their abode, the Cimmerians, who lived in subterranean dwellings.

Fig. 22 - A vision of Lake Avernus, a volcanic lake lying in the Italian region of Campania, as it appears today

And they served an oracle, hidden from view and set under the ground. An oracle which vaticinated by querying the dead, as Strabo recounts in his *Geographica*:

«Those who lived prior to our age applied to Lake Avernus the fairy tale about necromancy which is found in Homer, and so much so that they thought here was the oracle where the dead uttered prophecies as if they were alive: the oracle to which Ulysses came».

[In the Latin translation from the original Greek text: «Qui nos aetate antecesserunt, Necyae Homericæ fabulas Averno applicaverunt, atque adeo narrant fuisse ibi oraculum ubi vita defuncti responsa darent, eoque Ulissem advenisse»].

But who provided a bridge between the world of the dead and the living men who asked for responses?

It was a Sibyl.

Let's read from a remarkable excerpt taken from *Origo Gentis Romanae* (*The Origin of Roman People*), a fourth-century work attributed to Latin author Sextus Aurelius Victor. The passage depicts Aeneas after his arrival to Italy following the destruction of Troy:

«Aeneas buried on the shore the mother of Euxinus, one of his comrades, who had been carried off by old age, around the marsh which is between Misenus and Avernus, and that, thence, the name was assigned to the spot. And when he had discovered that in that very place a Sibyl chanted future events to mortals in the city which is called Cimbarionis, [they add that] he came to it, having inquired about the state of his own fortunes, and having been forbidden to bury in Italy his relative Prochyta, related to him by blood, whom he had left in good health. And afterwards he returned to the fleet and found she was dead in actual truth...».

[In the original Latin text: «Aeneam in eo litore Euxini cuiusdam comitis matrem ultime aetatis affectam circa stagnum, quod est inter Misenum Avernumque, extulisse atque inde loco nomen inditum; cumque comperisset ibidem Sibyllani mortalibus futura praecinere in oppido, quod vocatur Cimbarionis, venisse eo sciscitatum de statu fortunarum suarum aditisque fatis vetitum, ne is cognatam in Italia sepeliret Prochyta, cognatione sibi coniunctam, quam incolumem reliquerat. Et postquam ad classem rediit repperitque mortuam...»].

In the town of Cimmerians («Cimbarionis» in Strabo), hidden beneath the ground and set between Cape Misenus and the Lake of Avernus, there was a Sibyl, who vaticinated through the responses given by the dead.

At last, we have found the Cimmerian Sibyl: she was another Italian Sibyl, included in the classical list set down by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius, also including two other Sibyls from Italy, namely the Cumaean and the Tiburtine. And her abode was under the hills of Lake Avernus, not far from Cumae and Naples.

Fig. 23 - The *Origo Gentis Romanae* in an ancient edition printed in Paris in 1588, with the excerpt on the Sibyl prophesying near Lake Avernus

But what about the Cumaean Sibyl, whose shrine was also present in the very same area? And what about the alleged relationship - as stated by Francesco Maurolico in the sixteenth century - between the Cimmerian and the Apennine Sibyl, who was set in an utterly different region of Italy? Now, it seems to us that the pieces of the jigsaw puzzle are all coming together, and they indicate that no relation can be highlighted between the two Sibyls.

We will try to disentangle the above remaining questions in the next paragraph.

8. *Cumae, a land of netherworld gods*

After a close scrutiny of a number of ancient literary sources, we found out that the Cimmerian Sibyl belongs to the area of the Lake Avernus, in the Italian region of Campania: only a mile away from the traditional site

where the Cumaean Sibyl is said to have rendered her oracular responses by the ancient town of Cumae.

This result - which is already well known by scholars - should not be considered as unexpected. When we started our investigation, we noted, as many scholars did in the past, that in the classical enumeration of ten oracles set down by Lactantius the seventh Sibyl was the Cumaean («Cumana» in Latin), and the fourth the Cimmerian; however, in some versions of Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus* the fourth oracle appears with the attribute 'Cumean': a name that cannot but remind us of the antique town of Cumae, and an attribute providing a strong clue as to where to direct our research efforts.

And finally we caught the Cimmerian Sibyl in very region of Cumae. But why should there be two different Sibyls in the same area, a Cumaen and a Cimmerian?

First, we have to bear in mind the utterly peculiar nature of this portion of Italian land.

Let's fly over this corner of Campania, in southern Italy, by considering the attached map: we are hovering on a territory which is heavily, permanently marked by the mightiest subterranean powers in Europe. A land blessed - and doomed - by the Gods of the Netherworld.

Eastward of Cumae and Cape Misenus, since time immemorial, the ground has been ravaged by the fury of volcanoes. We are in the most renowned Phlegraean Fields, a large volcanic area hiding one of the most dangerous, and still active today, subterranean magmatic chambers in the world.

The Lake Avernus itself, at the center of the image, is a volcanic crater lake, once encircled by gloomy hills covered with mysterious woods. Strabo says that «the birds that cross the lake fall down into the waters, being killed by the vapours that rise from it, as it happens for places which are linked to the Netherworld» («aves quae supervolarent in aquam decidere, exanimatas aeris exhalatione, quemadmodum i Plutonijs locis fit» in Latin). A number of additional volcanic calderas (Mount Barbaro, the large Astroni crater, and many others) are present in the top side of the picture, including the small yet impressive Monte Nuovo ('The New

Mountain'), a tiny volcano which was created from nothing by a sudden eruption which took place between September, 29 and October, 6 1538. Earthquakes, emission of volcanic gases and measurable displacements of the ground (a phenomenon known as 'bradyseism') have always happened there.

Fig. 24 - The territory of Cumae in today's province of Campania (Italy)

No wonder that this land has always been considered as sacred to subterranean, divine powers. In Book 6 of his *Aeneid*, Publius Vergilius Maro sends Aeneas to the shore of Cumae, in search of the entryway to the underworld, «protected by the gloomy lake and the darkness of the woods» («tuta lacu nigro nemorumque tenebris» in Latin). And, according to many scholars, Lake Avernus was actually seen by ancient Romans as the entrance to Hades.

In this highly evocative context were rooted two different sibilline tradition: the Cumaean oracle and the Cimmerian oracle. However, both traditions, though documented through many literary passages drawn from a number of Latin and Greek authors, are not so easy to pinpoint from a storical and archeological points of view, as we will see in the next paragraph.

9. Cumaean and Cimmerian, a single Sibyl for Cumae

Cumae, one of the most ancient Greek colonies in southern Italy, established at the mid of the eighth century B.C., a town that was regarded as sacred to ctonian deities owing to its highly peculiar volcanic nature.

As we saw already, according to the available documents describing the traditions of ancient Rome, two sibilline oracles were to be found in Cumae: the Cumaean Sibyl and the Cimmerian Sibyl.

Fig. 25 - The Cumaean and the Cimmerian Sibyl as portrayed in manuscript Latin 920, a Book of Hour preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France and originally manufactured for Louis de Laval, a fifteenth-century French nobleman

Were they different Sibyls? Did they have any relationship one another? And are there any visible remnants of their shrines? What do contemporary archeology and modern history research have to tell us about them?

Let's consider the most famous prophetess, the Cumaean Sibyl: the seventh oracle in Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' classical list. She was also

celebrated by Vergilius in Book 6 of *Aeneid* with masterful verses: «terrific riddles she yells, as she sings in her cave, the truth enshrouded in darkness» [«Cumaea Sibylla - horrendas canit ambages antroque remugit - obscuris vera involvens» in Latin]. And we cannot forget the amazing portrait of a withered, ever-ageing Sibyl subject to a doom of immortality, as presented to us by Publius Ovidius Naso in his *Metamorphoses*, with a final stroke being painted by Gaius Petronius Arbiter, in his *Satyricon*, in which a shrunken Cumaean Sibyl, confined in a flask, asks visitors for a merciful death.

The literary tradition on the Cumaean Sibyl seems unmistakable, and it appears to depict some sort of oracle that really existed in ancient times.

However, the topic is not so easily managed. The Sibyl's Cave discovered in Cumae by an Italian archeologist, Amedeo Maiuri, in 1932 and shown to visitors in our present days is not recognised by scholars as the veritable site where the Cumaean Sibyl vaticinated. No archeological evidence of such an attribution has ever been found at the place. No positive, glaring oracular site has yet been identified in the existing area of ancient Cumae.

The actual problem is that, already in antique times, the Cumaean Sibyl was not active anymore. When Vergilius, Ovidius, Petronius and Lactantius wrote their works, the Sibyl had long transformed herself into a remote legend, lost in the mists of the past. Romans never knew nor saw this Sibyl in her actual reality, for she belonged to the long-gone Greek past of Cumae, a town which the Romans conquered in year 338 B.C., when four hundred years after its foundation had already elapsed. Rieuwerd Buitenwerf, a Dutch scholar, says with an incisive remark on the Cumaean oracle that «its location had already been forgotten by the time Virgil visited Cumae».

In the fourth century of the Christian era, Cumae had become a celebrated attraction for tourists who - just as today - wanted to see the site of the legendary Sibyl chanted by Vergilius. And sure enough the locals did not restrain themselves from telling paying visitors what they wanted to hear, as narrated in the *Exhortation to the Greeks* (Chapter 39), a Greek text once attributed to St. Justin Martyr:

«Easily you will learn the right religion from the ancient Sibyl, who used to teach through some kind of amazing inspiration by means of oracular predictions. [...] She, they say, rendered her prophecies in a city called Cumae, six miles from Baiæ (where the hot springs of Campania are found). When we arrived in this city, we saw a certain place where we discerned a huge basilica, hewn out of one rock [...] People who had received the local tradition from their own ancestors, told us that this was the very place where the prophetess used to utter her oracles. [...] When we were in the city, we learned these things ourselves from the ones who use to guide the visitors around to see the remarkable places in the area. They showed us also [...] a small artifact, made of bronze, in which they said her remains were kept».

Fig. 26 - The passages on the Cumaean Sibyl as taken from the *Exhortation to the Greeks*, written in the fourth century by an author named by scholars as Pseudo-Justin. The Latin-Greek edition shown in the figure was published in Oxford in 1703

[In the Latin translation from the original text in Greek: «Perfacile autem vobis erit rectam religionem [...] a veteri Sibylla ex afflatu quodam mirifico per sortes ac responsa vos docente percipere. [...] Eam in Campaniae [...] in urbe quadam cui Cumae nomen est, sexto a Baiis (qui locus thermas Campanas habet) lapide, oracula edidisse. Vidimus nos ea in urbe cum essemus, locum quendam, in quo ingentem basilicam, uno fabrefactam saxo contemplati sumus [...] ubi responsa eam dedisse affirmabant illi, qui res patrias a majoribus suis traditas acceperint. [...] Quin ipsi quoque, cum in urbe ea essemus, indicibus, qui hospites ad ea, quae visenda sunt, ducere solent, ostendentibus [...] vidimus loculum quendam ex aere elaboratum ubi reliquias ejus servari dicebant»].

So the actual, physical reality of the Cumaean Sibyl and her shrine appears to be lost forever, and that loss had already taken place at the time when Romans won Cumae for themselves.

And now, what about the Cimmerian Sibyl? If we start considering the Sibyl of the Cimmerians, the mist of history turns out to be even thicker. Let's try to dispel it, at least partially, in the next paragraph.

10. The Cimmerian Sibyl as an earlier Cumaean

When the Roman Empire was flourishing, the Cimmerians too had already become a legendary population long vanished from the sight of history, just like the Cumaean Sibyl who had disappeared centuries earlier. For the Romans themselves, Cimmerians were but a faint recollection: a legendary population whose subterranean abode, once concealed by the Lake Avernus, was extant no more already in the early Roman age. Not the least remnant of their subterranean dwellings and tunnels is to be found in our present days, and the more so if we consider the destructive earthquakes that have repeatedly been striking the area of Lake Avernus and the Phlegraean Fields across the centuries (for instance, the 1538 earthquake, when a small volcano, Monte Nuovo, was generated in a handful of days).

Despite all that, Strabo, who writes in the first century, reports an additional, remarkable detail:

«Later on the Cimmerians were destroyed by a certain king, because the response of the oracle did not turn out in his favour; the seat of the oracle, however, still endures, although it has been removed to another place».

[In the Latin translation from the original Greek text: «postea temporis Cimmerios fuisse deletos a rege quodam, cuius eventa oraculum non comprobassent, sedem oraculi alio translata etiamnum durare»].

Fig. 27 - Strabonis Rerum Geographicarum published in 1571 in Basel, with the excerpt on the Cimmerians

According to Strabo, at his age Cimmerians had already been wiped out centuries earlier. In another passage we already quoted, it's Strabo himself who adds that «Ephorus maintained that this site was of the Cimmerians, about whom he says that they dwell in underground premises» [«Ephorus vero Cimmeriis locum illum dicans, hos habitare ait in subterraneis aedificiis» in Latin]. And Ephorus was a local historian, who lived in Cumae during the fourth century B.C. (his books no longer exist).

This means that Cimmerians had vanished from Lake Avernus centuries and centuries before the arrival of the Romans in Cumae, but «the seat of the oracle, however, still endures, although it has been removed to another place».

Could it be that the Cimmerian Sibyl, who provided her responses in an underground site in Cumae by querying the dead through necromantic practices, had subsequently moved to another shrine, again situated in the town of Cumae, following the destruction of her original site, and that the Sibyl at the new site had taken the name of 'Cumaean'?

Could it be that the original, antique Cimmerian Sibyl had taken on the final attribute of 'Cumaean Sibyl', after having abandoned her former subterranean site, following its obliteration?

According to many scholars, the answer is positive. Jacques Hergon, a renowned French latinist, and other researchers (Luca Antonelli) consider the Cimmerian Sibyl as an early prophetess providing responses in the area of Cumae, by querying the dead through necromancy. Later on, after the destruction of her original underground shrine, the oracle moved to another temple in downtown Cumae, assuming the name of 'Cumaean Sibyl', providing her prophecies by writing them on a multiplicity of oak leaves, and then letting the leaves whirl freely in the whiffs of the wind («volent rapidis ludibria ventis», as Vergilius says), so as to render the oracular responses almost incomprehensible.

So, the Cimmerian Sibyl and the Cumaean Sibyl would actually be the same prophetess, the former being only an earlier name for the latter.

This identity would provide a full explanation for the suspicious confusion in the names attributed to the fourth Sibyl which arises in different versions of the list stated by Lactantius: 'Cimmeriam' in some of them, and 'Cumeam' in other manuscripts. In the suggested theory, the fourth Sibyl would be just identical to the seventh, the Cumaeam, but called by her original, more ancient name.

And another peculiar literary intricacy, connected to the description of the Cumaean Sibyl provided by Vergilius in his *Aeneid*, would find its correct solution.

In Book VI, Vergilius says that, after arriving in Cumae, «Aeneas the pious ascends the citadel which is ruled by glorious Apollo and heads to the ghastly, secret recesses, the huge cavern of the Sibyl» («pius Aeneas arces, quibus altus Apollo presidet horrendaque procul secreta Sibyllae antrum immane petit» in Latin). He is visiting what is to be identified with the Cumaean Sibyl, who provides her responses acting as the voice of Greek deity Apollo:

«Such reins Apollo shakes in the body of the frenzied prophetess, and such spurs he urges in her heart».

[In the original Latin text: «ea frena furenti concutit et stimolos sub pectore vertit Apollo»].

But then, later in the same Book, the Sibyl commands Aeneas to make an offering to Hecate, the Greek goddess associated to witchcraft and necromancy, and the rite is carried out at a cave by the Lake Avernus. Now, the Sibyl has taken on the full attributes of the older Cimmerian propheticess:

«A deep cave was there, with a huge, frighful opening, hard to reach, protected by the gloomy lake and the darkness of the woods [... Aeneas] put the offerings on the sacred fire, a prominent donation, appealing to Hecate by his voice, calling to the heaven and to vast Erebus».

[In the original Latin text: «Spelunca alta fuit vastoque inmanis hiatu, scrupea, tuta lacu nigro nemoremque tenebris [...] ignibus imponit sacris, libamina prima, voce vocans Hecaten caeloque Ereboque potentem»].

In the above excerpts, Vergilius would be just portraying the two aspects of the Cimmerian / Cumaean Sibyl: the necromantic propheticess (Cimmerian) and the oracle of Apollo (Cumaean). Two different aspects of the same Sibyl: the Sibyl of Cumae.

Fig. 28 - Aeneas and the Cumaean Sibyl portrayed in manuscript Vat Lat 3225 (folium 45v)

A Sibyl who re-emerges from the mists of a lost, almost forgotten past, as portrayed in a most precious illuminated manuscript (Vat. Lat. 3225) preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library in Rome: one of the most ancient manuscripted relics coming to us from the classical Roman world, dating back to the fourth century and featuring a stunning picture of Aeneas and his comrade Achates as they stand before the Cumaean Sibyl and her shrine dedicated to Apollo.

We are getting closer and closer to the end of our amazing journey into myth and sibilline lore. Time has come now to provide an answer to the initial question we had posed at the very beginning of our travel: is the Apennine Sibyl, the Sibyl of Norcia, connected in any way to the Cimmerian Sibyl, as alleged by a sixteenth-century abbot from Sicily, Francesco Maurolico, in his *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*?

The answer seems now to be clear. And we will detail it in the next article.

11. It's a long way from the Cimmerian Sibyl to the Apennines

When we began our investigation into the myth of the Cimmerian and Cumaean Sibyl, we started by considering a number of excerpts written by Francesco Maurolico in 1568.

In his *Topographia Sanctorum Christi Martyrum*, Maurolico states the following:

«The fourth Sibyl is the Cumaeam, whom Naevius mentions in his books about the Punic war, and Piso in his annals as well; from the Cimeriam castle, also known as the Cave of Norcia, which some call by the corrupted name of 'Cymea' or 'Cymica' [...] Cumae, a town of Campania lying by the gulf of Baiae. Here was the Cumaean Sibyl, who was also called Deiphobe, and by some named as Cimmeria or Cymica, but in truth the latter is a different one in the cavern of Norcia [...] Ameria, an Italian town set in the Sabine region. From this town the author names the 'Emerian Sibyl', who others call the 'Cimeriam' owing to the uncertainty of the place; she lives in the caverns of Norcia, and is different from both the Cumaean and the Tiburtine Sibyls».

When we started our exploration, we sensed that some kind of confusion affected Maurolico's words, with all his manifest efforts to corroborate the idea that the Apennine Sibyl, whose legend pertains to a cavern situated in the mountains raising in the vicinity of Norcia, in central Italy, should be identified with the fourth Sibyl in Lactantius' list, the Cimmerian.

Is Maurolico right?

The right answer is no. And possibly, from a certain point of view, yes.

Maurolico is right when he says that the Cimmerian or Cumeam or Chemical Sibyl, the fourth Sibyl, belongs to Cumae, as we ourselves have fully shown by our investigation. However, he is inconsistent when he says that the Cumaean is truly the Cimmerian, while in another passage he writes that the Cimmerian «is different from [...] the Cumaean».

In addition to that, he is wrong when he expresses all his confidence in the unfounded assumption that the Sibyl of Norcia is Lactantius' Cimmerian Sibyl, the fourth sibilline oracle in the list, basing his surmise on the name of a village allegedly set by the Cave of Norcia, whose name is - according to Maurolico - 'Cimerian' or 'Ameria'.

However, Maurolico's assumption is totally wrong. Because we have fully demonstrated that, in the antique tradition, the town of the Cimmerians was consistently situated by all ancient writers in Cumae, in the Italian province of Campania. Thus, Cimmerians had nothing to do with the Apennines, and equally they had nothing to do with Norcia. And the fourth Sibyl, the Cimmerian oracle, is not a Sibyl from Norcia, but a Sibyl from Cumae, as positively stated by all available classical authors.

Why did Maurolico incur this error?

His misleading statements appear to be the more perplexing if we consider that the identification of Cumae as the original place in which the fourth Cimmerian Sibyl vaticinated was not an unknown feature in Maurolico's times. Scholars of both his and later ages read the classical authors as we do today, and they found out the same pieces of information as we were able to retrieve in our present days: the Cimmerians lived by Cumae, and

they had their prophesying Sibyl, who was called 'Cimmerian' after their own name.

Let's take, for instance, a commentary written in 1523 by Juan Luis Vives, a great sixteenth-century Spanish scholar, a book published in Antwerp in 1576. In commenting a famous excerpt drawn from Augustine of Hippo's *The City of God* (Book XVIII, Chapter XXIII), in which Augustine enlists the Sibyls as pagan heralds of the Salvation, Juan Luis Vives reports the famous list of ten Sibyls originally contained in Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus*.

Fig. 29 - Augustine of Hippo's *De Civitate Dei* in a commented edition printed in Antwerp in 1576. The appendix includes a commentary written by Juan Luis Vives in 1523, in which a peculiar mention on the fourth Sibyl is found.

But, when he gets to the fourth Sibyl, he quotes the words by Lactantius with the addition of a highly remarkable sentence:

«The fourth [Sibyl is] Cumaean in Italy, whom Naevius mentions in his book on the Punic war, and Piso in his annals. Some call her Italian, from the Cimmerian town which is not far from Cumae in the Campania province».

[In the original Latin text: «Quarta [Sibylla est] Cumaea in Italia, quam Naevius in libris belli Punici, Piso in annalibus nominat. Hanc alij Italicam nuncupant, ex Cimerio Campaniae vicino Cumis oppido»].

Juan Luis Vives could not have been clearer than that: the fourth Sibyl is an Italian oracle from a small town near Cumae. And the town's name - as we know from antique authors - is Cimmerian.

And let's consider another work released a century later, the *Lexicon Geographicum* (*Geographical Dictionary*) published by a French scholar, Michel Antoine Baudrand, in 1652. Under letter 'C', we find another clear reference to the town of the Cimmerians:

«Cimmerians, population of Campania, in the vicinity of Baiiae and the Lake of Avernus, whose town was called Cimmerian, where the Sibyl's cave is, 'la grotta della Sibilla' [in Italian], 1 mile from Baiiae and 3 miles from Pozzuoli».

Fig. 30 - Michel Antoine Baudrand's *Lexicon Geographicum* published in Paris in 1652, including an entry on Cimmerians

[In the original Latin text: «Cimmerij item, pop. Campaniae, apud Baias et lacum Avernum, quorum opp. Cimmerium fuit, ubi antrum Sibyllae, 'la grotta della Sibilla', a Baiis 1 a Puteolis 3 milia passuum»].

Again, in the seventeenth century too the Cimmerians were placed in the vicinity of Lake Avernus, very far from central Apennines, where Norcia lies.

And here is another interesting example coming to us from a century later. In 1767, an Italian nobleman and scholar, Cesare Orlandi, who was born in an Umbrian town and whose family originated from the province of Marche, published an updated edition of a famous work, the *Iconologia*, originally edited by Cesare Ripa in 1593. In his own revised edition, Cesare Orlandi included a whole section on Sibyls, and the following is what he wrote on the Cimmerian:

«Cumean Sibyl, or Cimmerian: [...] she was born in Cumae, or in a Cimmerian village in the surroundings of Cumae, in the countryside of Naples. Many call her Italic, and it is reputed that she was vaticinating in Italy after the great fire of Troy; and of her, with full reason, we can reckon that she is the same as the Cumaean. Actually many authors report that this Sibyl was the Cumaean, to whom Vergilius pretends his characters turned for advice in Book 6 of his *Aeneid*».

[In the original Italian text: «Sibilla Cumea, ovvero Cimmeria: [...] Sibilla Cumea, ovvero Cimmeria: [...] Costei nacque in Cuma, o in Cimmerio paese vicino a Cuma nella Campagna di Napoli. Da molti è chiamata Italica, e si crede che abbia vaticinato in Italia poco dopo l'incendio di Troia; e di questa con tutta ragione si può pensare che fosse la stessa che la Cumana. Di più, non pochi riferiscono, che fosse Costei quella Sibilla, alla quale finge Virgilio nel lib. 6 'Eneid.' di esser ricorso per consiglio»].

Does Cesare Orlandi write that the Cimmerian Sibyl has any connection with a Sibyl in Norcia? Not at all. And this fact is of remarkable significance: because Cesare Orlandi was born in Città della Pieve, an Umbrian town, and his family came from Fermo, in the Marche region; if any relation had really existed between the Cimmerian and a Sibyl from Norcia - a town sitting between Umbria and Marche - Orlandi would certainly know, and would certainly tell. But he does not.

Fig. 31 - Cesare Ripa's *Iconology* in a revised and extended version edited by Cesare Orlandi in Perugia in 1767, with a section on Sibyls including a passage on the Cimmerian Sibyl

Thus, no doubt can still remain as to whether late-Renaissance scholars and later men of letters were fully informed about the true origin of the Cimmerian Sibyl: they knew that she had vaticinated in the area of Cumae, and no relation to the Apennines could be established in any way.

Fig. 32 - The fourth Sibyl, Cumean or Cimmerian, as portrayed in the 1767 edition of Cesare Ripa's *Iconologia*

Definitely, Maurolico proves to be on the wrong side. But why was he so confident in his belief that the Apennine Sibyl was Lactantius' fourth Sibyl?

Though we have no conclusive information on that specific aspect, we will try to end our search with a few final considerations, which we will state in the next (and last) article.

12. The path towards the true origin of the sibilline myth

We made a long journey across the centuries in search of the fourth Sibyl, the Cimmerian. We started from Francesco Maurolico, a sixteenth-century Sicilian abbot, and we went as far back as Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius and other classical Latin and Greek authors including Silius Italicus, Sextus Pompeius Festus, Pliny the Elder, Lycophrone of Chalcis, Sextus Aurelius Victor, Publius Vergilius Maro, St. Justin Martyr and Strabo. We have perused the works of Andrea da Barberino, Filippo Barbieri, the Muslim astronomer Albumazar, the fifteenth-century *Oracula Sibyllina*, and excerpts from later authors such as Juan Luis Vives, Michel Antoine Baudrand and Cesare Orlandi.

We have demonstrated that all the clues which refer to the Cimmerian Sibyl lead to Cumae, in the Italian province of Campania. Only abbot Francesco Maurolico seems to depart from this unanimous view, as he alone asserts that the fourth Sibyl, the Cimmerian, is in truth the Apennine Sibyl of Norcia.

At the present stage of our search, we do not have any clue as to why Maurolico (and apparently only Maurolico) holds such belief. We could not retrieve any other earlier literary source conveying the same idea.

However, some pattern begins to appear amid the literary works, excerpts, passages, and mentions providing references to the world of the sibilline oracles: the Apennine Sibyl seems to present some kind of veiled, undeciphered connection to the Cumaean / Cimmerian Sibyl, as assumed by Andrea da Barberino in his fifteenth-century romance “Guerrino the Wretch” and Francesco Maurolico in his “Topographia”.

That is, some cryptic link is apparently arising between the Apennines, set in the vicinity of Norcia, and Cumae.

We still don't know what this relation might be. Better than that, we already hold a specific idea on this highly fascinating subject, but this idea is still untold. An obscure surmise which “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” will reconsider and develop in future articles, not yet published.

Fig. 33 - The trail which leads to the legendary peak of Mount Sibyl, enshrouded in shadows

For the time being, we are leaving the reader with the suggestions connected to the ancient, long-vanished town of the Cimmerians, with all its mysterious spell that has bewitched men of letters of all times. A mystery we have tried to shed light upon, by walking the narrow paths traced by many authors of essays, romances and poems throughout many centuries.

An arcane travel which we want to conclude with the words written by the greatest poet of all, Homer, in his epic poem *Odyssey*. There, in Book 11, he speaks of the gloomy mystery of the Cimmerians:

«She [Odysseus' ship] came to deep-flowing Oceanus, that bounds the Earth, where is the land and city of the Cimmerians, wrapped in mist and cloud. Never does the bright sun look down on them with his rays either when he mounts the starry heaven or when he turns again to earth from heaven, but baneful night is spread over wretched mortals».

Odysseus lands «to the place of which Circe had told us»: «the house of Hades», where he performs the most frightful of all rites, the summoning of the dead from the Underworld, a gloomy ritual known as 'nekya'.

The Apennine Sibyl, the Cumaean Sibyl, the Cimmerian Sibyl, the Underworld. A legendary mystery that appears to be rooted in the deepest recesses of time, and human mind.

Michele Sanvico